

Chemical cleaning of a turbo-generator condenser

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Abstract—The following paper is meant to analyse the results of a chemical treatment to the "NG H2/630S" Brazilian turbo-condenser in the sugar industry. A team of chemical engineers, electrical engineers and mechanics made able to identify leaks in a such delicate process, as distributing energy. We guaranteed that the procedures were followed correctly and verified step by step the calculations made, to welfare our company goods by using less for better. Chemicals aren't cheap and its important to make a good use of them; solutions of hydrochloric acid, ammonium bi-fluoride in powder, calcium carbonate and plenty of water cleanses were used and made this method a success. We guaranteed a full operative turbo-condenser for the harvest season of 2023-2024, full-filling the results expected by the users.

I. INTRODUCTION

Steam quality depends on water quality, boiler designs and operating procedures; it's a law for turbines used in energy generation. The accumulation of incrustation in turbines due to impurities in the steam can cause thermodynamic and mechanical problems that can cause vane breakage, if chlorine is present. This means that it is essential to remove chlorine and their components, for example, $MgCl_2$ and $NaCl$, from the steam. It has been proven that an amount equal to or greater than 0.0025% of chlorine is dangerous because at high temperatures, it attacks the steel alloys; material vanes and nozzles are manufactured with. [8]

Other causes that influence the quality of the steam are: overloads, exceeding the maximum steam production level and having considerably higher pressures than the admissible operating pressure. When considering the cost of water treatment, we must also be taken into account shut-downs and repairs of the turbine, resulting from breakdowns caused by steam impurity [8].

To our disposal we have a turbine condensation model with a unique housing and a controlled extraction, that is used to action an electrical energy generator (Genisa®, 3-phase, 20MW-synchronous generator) [8] through a velocity reducer (Renkzanini®Ta 63 n reducer) [8]. This type of turbo-generator can work aisle or parallel a counter pressure or even with the company network. It has a principal valve, an emergency valve, 4 control valves following a sequential aperture. As consequence of the kinetic energy made from the momentum the vapour has as it enters the turbine, it sets in motion the velocity reducer and consequently changes into mechanical energy that thanks to our synchronous generator, it

is able to transform into electrical energy and distribute energy to the sector circuit [8].

The steam that leaves the turbine is divided in two, first a controlled pressure (25 psig) which is reused in the sugar industry to feed the evaporation process, which condensates are used and treated for a partial closed cycle. Secondly and the ease of interest of this paper, we have the residual condensates which pass through a system of condensation which includes the principal condensation tubular interchanger with a vacuum system, made through a vacuum pump (previously ejectors) and a secondary phase which has a control level and condensate pumps. We will eager on a chemical cleaning method realized to pursue reusable condensates without incrustations on the heat interchanger, and guarantee the ideal conductivity, pH and minerals values [8].

II. THEORETICAL TOOLS

A. Corrosion of hydrochloric acid

Acids are common substances which dissociate hydrogen ions, H^+ , or formally called, oxonium ion, H_3O^+ , in the aqueous solutions.

Hydrochloric acid is a strong acid and understanding the concepts of neutralization is a very crucial topic for treating supply water, waste-water, and preventing metallic corrosion in various industrial processes.

Hydrochloric acid is among the strongest acids, with a 0.92 degree of dissociation @25°C and 0.1N. Generally, pH at higher temperatures acidifies faster than at a lower temperatures and even in a neutral pH, higher hydrogen ion concentration at higher temperatures often accelerates the metallic corrosion in the system. [1]

Naturally, magnesium chloride is presented in water and is hydrolysed to hydrochloric acid on the heating surface by:

The magnesium hydroxide in (2) and the ferrous chloride in (3) react together as shown in the reaction and produce

magnesium chloride again. Then carbon steel is corroded again.

As shown, chloride ions are avoided, its important to know that the amount of hydrochloric acid should be the specified, and the solution must be diluted at the ideal conditions.

If a sufficient amount of alkali is maintained in the boiler water, it immediately neutralizes the hydrochloric acid produced and no corrosion happens. If neutralization is obtained correctly then the water acidifies and corrosion will damage the equipment.

B. Erosion and corrosion of ammonia

Structure material is fundamental for the tube condenser, nevertheless water treatment is also important to minimize the erosion-corrosion, caused by:

1. Low pH.
2. Higher concentration of dissolved oxygen.
3. Suspended solids.

The erosion-corrosion is minimized by controlling basic pH. Condenser tubes are usually made from copper/copper alloys where on the side of the tubes, corrosion is usually caused by ammonia and oxygen dissolved in the steam or by the impingement of steam and the mechanical vibrations [1].

When non-condensed gases, such as ammonia and oxygen are contained in the steam, they are highly concentrated near the air ejector and copper is attacked by the following reactions:

The condensate that flows through the tubes, like the surrounding baffle plates, contain ammonia and oxygen, and over a long time, they are severely attacked [1]. Therefore, an outstanding treatment is required to avoid an overdose of ammonia used for pH control and oxygen removal. The erosion-corrosion due to the impingement with steam occurs at the most upper part of the tubular condenser where steam enters the system and also condensate that rises due to high velocity, besides mechanical damage on tubes occur when the spacing of baffle plates is inappropriate.

C. Corrosion of carbonic acid

Using carbonate solutions should be properly used; bicarbonate and carbonate ions decompose to carbon dioxide gas.

The high solubility of carbon dioxide blends to the steam and condensate line along with steam, and dissolves as carbonic acid H_2CO_3 when the steam is condensed [1].

If the condensate contains acidic solutions the pH is significantly reduced. A weak acid as carbonic acid will reduce pH due to the weak pH buffering action.

The carbonic acid produced by reaction (10) could corrode the iron carbon steel by the following reaction:

Under the pressure of dissolved oxygen, the reproduction of carbon dioxide speeds corrosion.

In order to prevent corrosion on the condensate line, the next instructions should be followed [1]:

- 1) Dealkalization or a softening treatment must be used in order to remove or decrease carbonate growth.
- 2) Use of pH inhibitors (volatile amines.)
- 3) Use of corrosion inhibitors (filming amines.)
- 4) Removal of dissolved oxygen (scavenger and de-aerators.)

III. PREPARING THE CONDENSER

The purpose of cleansing the condenser is to eliminate incrustations and identifying leaks that could contaminate its condensates, but before calculating chemicals we must know the condenser body to avoid posterior damages. [14]

- 1) Identify the condenser tubes alloy.
- 2) Identify if there are no stainless tubes; in case of having, isolate by means of plates or rubberised plugs.
- 3) Isolate water recirculation lines to the condenser.
- 4) Have manometers and thermometers or thermocouples in order to read pressure and temperature.
- 5) Enable pumps, pipes, warehouse containers, sampling points, drains and have the right illumination.
- 6) Enable a steam supply or a heat source.

IV. PREPARING THE CHEMICALS

A. General Procedure

The following cleaning consist of the following steps [14]:

- 1) Determine the system volume and status.
- 2) Acidic phase.
- 3) Passivation phase.
- 4) Mechanical cleaning.
- 5) Hydrostatic test.

Fig. 1. Tubular heat exchanger [15]

B. System volume

Two ways of measuring the tube condenser volume are available.

1) Mathematical methods

We must understand the properties of a tubular exchanger which is illustrated as Fig. 1.

There are two areas of interest for the volumes, first the tube bundle (area of interest for the cleansing) and the shell, where the steam will circulate and eventually condense.

In order to know the volume of the condenser the following information is needed:

- Nominal tube size or the outer diameter (OD) or inner diameter (ID) of the tubes.
- Material of the tubes.
- BWG of the tubes.
- Length of the tubes
- Number of tubes

Once obtaining this data, proceed to use the following formulas and charts:

- Finding ID, OD and thickness of a tube using pipe charts.

Usually the provider gives the nominal size or OD of the tube. With the nominal size (or OD) and BWG of the tube, use Appendix A.5-2, page 1008, in Transport Processes and Separation Process Principles (Includes Unit Operations) 4th Edition by Christie John Geankoplis [3].

- Cross-sectional area of a pipe (cylinder.) Use Appendix A.5-2 of Geankoplis [3], or the following formula:

$$A = \pi/4 * D^2 \quad (15)$$

D: For the inner section, use ID; for the outer, OD.

- Volume of a tube

$$V = A * L \quad (16)$$

L: Length of the tube.

Using ID and multiplying it by the total tubes will result in the tube bundle volume (TBV) which is the theoretical total volume for the cleansing. Using OD will result in the total volume for the heat exchange.

Note that by subtracting the TBV to the total volume, the shell volume is obtained.

2) Practical methods

The first method is versatile having the required measurements, nevertheless no two systems are alike and your heat exchanger may be damaged or deteriorated for which there is also a practical method to compare the results and use a mean.

- Fill up the tubular exchanger with de-mineralized water, it could be inverse osmosis water.
- Let water flow through the heat exchanger and container available and drain this water at first, in order to remove any residues. Then for 1 hour let water recirculate using pumps.
- Check if there are no leaks in the containers, pipes, connections, condenser, etc.

After doing these steps, close the entrance valves to the container, make sure to have an approximate volume of the condenser, close all drains, and fill up the condenser with water, after filling it up, close the entrance valves to the tubular exchanger and open the valve to the tank, measure the tank diameter and the height of the water in order to find an approximate volume (use (15) and (16).)

Compare both volumes and obtain a mean if necessary.

C. Acidic phase

Before starting any chemical phase, make sure your team has the following security equipment:

- Gas mask.
- Safety goggles.
- Nitrile chemical resistant gloves.
- Apron.

The next chemicals are necessary and should be added in the following order to continue with the acidic phase:

- Make sure to have a container that has space for the TBV and fill it out with the that volume.
- Its recommended to calculate the saturation point whenever any solid is applied to a liquid in order to guarantee that no precipitates are going to be formed. If formed, calculations will vary.

To know the solubility of a solid in a fluid you have many ways:

- Know the solubility constant of the solid (Ksp) and calculate the solubility by the ions dissociation [10].
- Using solubility graphs or tables as the ones available at the Perry's chemical engineers' handbook [2].

- c) Use the technical sheets provided.
- 3) Raise the water temperature at 45°C with steam or a heat source.
 - 4) Add up carbon/stainless steel or copper inhibitor (depending on your alloy) at 0.5% w/w. Let it dilute for 10 minutes.
 - 5) Then add ammonium bi-fluoride at 2% w/w. Let it dilute for 20 minutes.
 - 6) At last, add hydrochloric acid at 5% w/w. We will assume that the solids previously added are totally soluble and the they do not increase, neither affect the TBV.
 - 7) Let the fluids flow for 1hr and 30mins.
 - 8) Identify there are no leaks, if present, be careful. In case of having spilled acid due to the leaks, neutralize it with calcium carbonate, do not add water.
 - 9) After the time required, drain the solution [14].

D. Passive (Neutralizing) phase

In order to passivate the acid we must add Na₂CO₃ to weaken HCl and start to neutralize the system condition by the following reaction [10]:

Note that HCl is a strong acid and its possible you ill need to recirculate and drain water until you have neutral conditions.

- 1) Fill your container tank with the TBV.
- 2) Add the required sodium carbonate to have a solution at 10% p/p.
- 3) Recirculate the solution for 1 hour.
- 4) Measure pH constantly until obtaining pH values similar to the mineralized water used.
- 5) Drain the water.

Note that the drained water could be treated in a water treatment plant.

E. Mechanical Cleaning

In order to finish the cleansing of the condenser, you must open it and clean it with a pressure washer which works with manipulated water flow and pressurized air to be able to give the necessary touch to the circular brush. It enables to clean the left incrustations inside each tube [14].

F. Hydrostatic test

A typical hydrostatic test is a pressure test in which the system is pressurized and it evaluates its integrity and infrastructure. The test is conducted at a pressure, PT (minimum test gauge pressure), of 1.5 times the design pressure, P, times a temperature correction factor. The temperature correction factor compensates for the fact that the test may be conducted at a lower temperature, where the material has a higher strength than at the design condition [13].

After completing of the hydrostatic tests, the water should be immediately drained.

Another practical way is using the RECON 2500 Leak Test gun which is consisted of two guns sealing both sides of the tube in the heat exchanger. One air injection gun and plugging gun are provided pressurizing the tube. When test pressure is achieved a seal on both sides is obtained, if the pressure set at the pressure gage is constant, there is no leak, if pressure decreases, there is a leak. For more information follow the manual [11].

V. EQUATIONS

1) Diluting solids into liquids [10]

a) Solubility

A solution concentration is described as:

$$C = \frac{msolute}{vsolvent} \quad (18)$$

at a specific temperature.

A solution could be:

i) Unsaturated If:

$$Cr - Cs < 0 \quad (19)$$

ii) Saturated If:

$$Cr - Cs = 0 \quad (20)$$

iii) Supersaturated If:

$$Cr - Cs > 0 \quad (21)$$

Where Cr is the real concentration and Cs is the saturated concentration at a specific temperature. Note that concentration is dependant on temperature.

C could be any concentration unit for mass/volume (ex. g/L) or the amount of substance/volume (ex. mol/L.)

b) %W/W

After calculating the solubility of the solid dissolved in your solvent, and by knowing your saturation state, you can now proceed to calculate the mass of solid needed to obtain the % w/w required in the TBV.

$$\% \frac{W}{W} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [\%solute_n * msolute_n]}{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [msolute_n] + msolvent} \quad (22)$$

Note that every technical sheet will have the %solute purity of your compounds. Sometimes more than 1 provider is available and you can have more than one %purity and a summatory is needed.

2) Liquid-Liquid dilutions

Liquid-liquid solutions often require more data than solid-liquid due to the fact liquids are not additive as they depend on the molecular properties of the liquid. Data such as density, miscibility and polarity is required. A simple rule is that "like dissolves like", in our case water is a polar covalent compound such as hydrochloric

acid, so miscibility is high and no calculations are needed [10].

In the case of cleaning a heat exchanger the total volume will not depend on the liquids, instead on the TBV. By knowing the %concentration needed in the solution we have a 2x2 matrix ready to be solved.

Equation 1:

$$TBV = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [V s_n] + V_{sv} \quad (23)$$

Where: s= solute; sv= solvent

TBV: Tubular bundle volume

Equation 2:

In liquids, its simpler to measure volume than its mass so we substitute the density formula in (22).

$$\rho = \frac{m}{V} \quad (24)$$

Note: Density is depends on temperature.

- Hydrochloric acid

If no density is given by the technical sheet, use the Perry's Manual Section 2, Table 2.59 for hydrochloric acid solutions at different % and temperatures [2].

Note: an interpolation may be required.

- Water

Use the Perry's Manual Section 2-30, Density (kg/m³) of Saturated Liquid Water from the Triple Point to the Critical Point, interpolation may be needed. Also Table 2-32 Densities of Inorganic and Organic Liquids (mol/dm³); using the next polynomial [2]:

For water over the entire temperature range of 273.16 to 647.096 K.

$$\rho = 17.863 + 58.606\tau^{0.35} - 95.396\tau^{2/3} + 213.89\tau - 141.26\tau^{4/3} \quad (25)$$

where:

$$\tau = 1 - T/647.096 \quad (26)$$

Where density is in mol/dm³ and T is in K.

Note: Polynomials often give approximate data, tables with real data are more precise.

Substituting (24) in (22) we have:

$$\% \frac{W}{W} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [\%s_n * V s_n * \rho s_n]}{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [V s_n * \rho s_n] + V_{sv} * \rho_{sv}} \quad (27)$$

Where: s= solute; sv= solvent

Solving a 2x2 Equation

- Cramer's rule

We have 2 unknown variables which are Vs and Vsv, a 2x2 matrix using cramer's rule will be the ideal mathematical way of solving and acknowledging the amount of hydrochloric acid and water we must dilute.

$$\begin{cases} a_1x + b_1y = c_1, \\ a_2x + b_2y = c_2. \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_1b_2 - a_2b_1 \quad (29)$$

$$D_x = \begin{vmatrix} c_1 & b_1 \\ c_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix} = c_1b_2 - c_2b_1 \quad (30)$$

$$D_y = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & c_1 \\ a_2 & c_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_1c_2 - a_2c_1 \quad (31)$$

$$x = \frac{D_x}{D}; y = \frac{D_y}{D} \quad (32)$$

Where a, b, c are independent variables and x and y are the two unknown variables; x=Vs; y=Vsv. In order to solve a re-order in (27) must be made.

- Alternative Ways

Nowadays simplified solvers exist which make easier to solve multi-variable equations. Use a solver in a calculator, MS Excel or your program of preference.

VI. CALCULATION RESULTS

The following section is a summary of the condenser structure; chemicals available, properties and the results of the use of the equations previously explained.

A. Tubular Condenser

The following data was provided by NG Metalúrgica PY-1700-6600-NXN condenser [9].

TABLE I
TURBO-GENERATOR OPERATIONAL CONDITIONS

Technical Properties		
Property	Shell	Tube bundle
Fluid	Steam	Cooling water
Flow [kg/h]	41,200	1,857,000
Work pressure [kgf/cm ²]	0.178 (ABS)	3.0
Project pressure [kgf/cm ²]	1.0(vacuum)	3.0
Hydrostatic cold pressure [kgf/cm ²]	1.3	8.19
Hydrostatic hot pressure [kgf/cm ²]	1.3	7.17
Work cold pressure [kgf/cm ²]	2.11	6.3
Work hot pressure [kgf/cm ²]	1.77	5.52
Temperature in [°C]	57	28
Temperature out [°C]	57	40
Project temperature [°C]	57	40
Joint efficiency	0.7	0.7
Corrosion margin [mm]	1.5	1.5
Number of baffles	1	2
Isolation	No	No
NR-13 Classification	C-Class, Group 3, Category 3	
Heat transfer [kcal/hr]	22,289,200	
Outer surface [m ²]	366.0	

^aCHS-Coolers and heates systems Ind. e Com. LTDA.

In order to verify the data provided you could use Fourier Series (Note: Use Geankoplis Chapter 4 for a better understanding [3])

$$\frac{q_x}{A} = -k \frac{\delta T}{\delta x} \quad (33)$$

Or in its simplified design equation for calculating heat transfer:

$$q = UA\Delta Tl_m \quad (34)$$

where:

$$\Delta Tl_m = \frac{\Delta T_2 - \Delta T_1}{\ln(\Delta T_2/\Delta T_1)} \quad (35)$$

and for counter-current flows:

$$\Delta T_2 = Th_o - Tc_i; \Delta T_1 = Th_i - Tc_o \quad (36)$$

For the data provided we could use (35) and find the logarithmic temperature.

Note: We have 1 baffle in the shell and 2 baffles in the tubes (1-2), for a correction factor in temperature use Figure 4.9-4 in Geankoplis [3] [4] [6].

$$Z = \frac{Th_i - Th_o}{Tc_o - Tc_i}; Y = \frac{Tc_o - Tc_i}{Th_i - Tc_i} \quad (37)$$

After finding the correction factor you will multiply it to your logarithmic temperature to obtain your real logarithmic temperature value, in our case, due to the fact steam just condenses, the graph tends to give an F_T value of 1, so its the same value. Afterwards normal calculations may proceed.

$$q = U_i A_i \Delta T_m = U_o A_o \Delta T_m \quad (38)$$

where:

$$\Delta T_m = F_T \Delta Tl_m \quad (39)$$

For the area you can have two interests, A_i and A_o . Where A_i is area of the inner surface of the wall that separates the two fluids, and A_o is the area of the outer surface of the wall.

$$A_i = \pi ID * L; A_o = \pi OD * L \quad (40)$$

For the total area, multiple it by the number of tubes.

In order to calculate q, an energy balance must be made, you should obtain:

$$q = \dot{m}_w C_{p_w} \Delta T_w = \dot{m}_s \Delta h f g_s \quad (41)$$

Where w stands for the cooling water and s for the steam flow.

In order to find C_{p_w} you must use Table 2-153 in [J/kmol K] from Perry's manual for water [2].

$$C_{p_L} = C1 + C2T + C3T^2 + C4T^3 + C5T^4 \quad (42)$$

And for hfg_s use Table A-5 Tables of properties, figures and diagrams (SI units) in Thermodynamics: An Engineering Approach, 9th edition. Copyright ©2019 by Yunis A. Çengel [7].

Note: Temperatures or at least one flow is needed to follow this method in other cases, use Chapter 4 of Geankoplis [3].

Using Appendix A.5-2 in Geankoplis [3] and by knowing OD, material and thickness.

- 1) OD: 1-1/4" or 31.75mm
- 2) Material: SA-214-02 (Carbon steel)
- 3) Thickness: 2.11mm
- 4) BWG: 14
- 5) ID: 27.53mm
- 6) Length: 5394mm
- 7) Total amount: 684
- 8) TBV = 2.19619 m³ or 2196.19L

From the balance previously explained we obtained the following data using the temperatures and flows provided by the technical sheet.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta Tl_m &= 22.47 \\ U_o &= 11,272.53 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K} \\ C_{p_w,av} &= 4.183 \text{ kJ/kgK} \end{aligned}$$

TABLE II
TURBO-GENERATOR ENERGY BALANCE

Comparison chart				
Property	Technical sheet	Balance	% Error	Tables
Heat transfer; q [kcal/hr]	22,289,200.0	22,262,444.1	0.120	
Enthalpy; hfg_w [kJ/kg]	2,265.06	2,262.34	0.634	2,248.09
Outer surface; A_o [m ²]	366.0	368.01	0.540	

Note: The U_o is within range of steam, according to W.H McAdams, Heat Transmission, ed. 3, page 5 [3] and Geankoplis Table 4.1-2 [3].

The specific heat of water is averaged to simplify calculations.

B. Physiochemical properties

- 1) General properties

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TBV} &= 2196.19\text{L} \\ T &= 45^\circ\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

Note: The mineralized water added at first (to the inhibitor and ammonium) will be the necessary water to obtain the TBV summing up the hydrochloric acid volume. Your first calculation should be the 2x2 matrix.

- 2) Mineralized water

- a) ρ : 990.17 kg/m³
- b) Mineralized water volume: 1892.670L

- 3) Lithsolvent 620 (Inhibitor)

- a) Purity: 98%
- b) Solubility at 20°C: 1000 kg/m³
- c) %w/w= 0.5%
- d) Lithsolvent added: 9.611kg

- 4) Ammonium bi-fluoride

- a) Purity: 98%
- b) Solubility at 20°C: 630 kg/m³
- c) %w/w= 2%
- d) Ammonium bi-fluoride added: 39.044kg

- 5) Hydrochloric Acid

Two hydrochloric solutions were available for this cleansing. We had 2 barrels of 210.52L of a 31.5% solution and 1 barrel of a 32% solution.

- a) Solution 1
 - i) Purity: 31%
 - ii) ρ_{\min} : 1,140 kg/m³
 - iii) ρ_{\max} : 1,190 kg/m³
 - iv) ρ_{mean} : 1,165 kg/m³
 - v) %w/w= 5%
 - vi) Hydrochloric acid added: 303.52L

- b) Solution 2
 - i) Purity: 33%
 - ii) ρ_{\min} : 1,159 kg/m³
 - iii) ρ_{\max} : 1,169 kg/m³
 - iv) ρ_{mean} : 1,164 kg/m³
 - v) %w/w= 5%
 - vi) Hydrochloric acid added: 0L

Calculations proved we just needed approximately two barrels (1.39) of the 31.5% solution.

6) Calcium carbonate

After draining the previous solution, mineralized water with the TBV should be added.

- a) Purity: 99%
- b) Solubility at 20°C: 1000 kg/m³
- c) %w/w= 10%
- d) Calcium carbonate added: 210.571kg

VII. OBSERVATIONS

Many unexpected situations occurred in the process, which fortunately we were aware that could happen.

- 1) For every action there is an equal and opposite reaction: After we fulfilled our container with the water calculated, we started adding the inhibitor for 10 minutes. Afterwards we added the ammonium bi-fluoride and let it flow for 20 minutes. After adding hydrochloric acid our leaks were revealed, and an unexpected flow of hydrochloric acid started spilling out of the condenser and fell to the floor. As theory previously explained, the team rapidly started adding calcium carbonate to neutralize the solution and stopped the pumps; it was the first chemical cleaning ever with acid to the condenser and thanks to the theory of chemistry known, no one was harmed.
- 2) Let the acid flow, do not throw it away: After letting the acid flow through a few minutes and watching the leaks, we stopped the pumps and sent the solution back to the tank. Then we rinse the condenser with water so it was safe to identify the leaks in the condenser and welded them.
- 3) Continue with the chemical cleaning: We continued with the cleaning and no further dangerous leaks were seen. We let the solution flow for 1 hour and 30 minutes and then drain all the acidic solution. Then we prepared the calcium carbonate solution and let it flow for 1 hour and 20 minutes. We measure the solution pH and it was 11.42. Then we drained the solution and rinse it with water until we guaranteed to have a pH as the mineralized water which was 6.5. Apparently the

tubes seemed corroded but it was all the incrustation torn off.

4) Appearances may lie:

After draining the solution a mechanical cleanse was made and the results were the expected, an almost new tube bundle, meaning the cleansing was a success. The cooling water used during harvest season is river water with no treatment, and as explained in the theoretical section, this water has a lot of contaminants we don't want to mix with the steam, and consequently with the condensate, entering the boiler and pausing all the plant due to a erroneous water treatment.

5) Leaks:

Out of the 684 tubes, 19 were with leaks, which 8 tubes where from the vacuum zone.

6) Harvest 2023-2024:

During harvest 2023-2024, no leaks were identified and the cleaning was a success. According to calculations and technical sheets, for 110,000 kg/hr, the condenser recovers 37.45% of the steam produced, nevertheless, the pumps connected form condenser's hot well to the de-aerator didn't had the enough power to defeat the de-aerators pressure and caused a vacuum from the pipe lines, and the water from the condenser had to be deviated and couldn't be used as part of the condensates, which make the harvest season difficult when this condenser was used. A new system is going to be applied in order to optimize the condensates.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Chemical cleansings are essential but dangerous. In case of overdosing chemicals, damage in your equipments may occur, so a verification of calculations are needed. In case of having stainless tubes, the acidic phase could have a negative effect so its important to verify their existence and isolate them. In industry many providers exist, and they will persuade to buy their products in the quantities provided by them. Providers make approximations and not exact values, is your responsibility as a collaborator to optimize your resources.

After the chemical cleaning an obvious change with respect to the condenser incrustations were seen. The inhibitor helped the tubes walls not to be affected by the acid. After the passive phase, incrustations seemed to be eliminated, but the tubes were still dirty. The mechanical wash made evident the cleaning and the hydrostatic test verified which tubes had leaks. There were 19 tubes that had to be covered and welded due to the fact that when the hydrostatic test was made, pressure changes were noted.

The condenser performance is expected lower its quality since the vacuum tubes were the most affected after washing since of the 19 tubes, 8 correspond to this high demand area. This area only has 60 tubes, and 2 were already welded, meaning we expect a 13.80% more of deficiency in the zone. The total heat transfer efficiency will decrease to a total of 2.78%, but the vacuum zone is critical to condense steam, if this zone is affected it means the level requires to start up the

turbine will fill up in less time causing delays in the turbine start, or even during operation its efficiency will be lowered and suffered.

This lets the company with a crucial lecture, chemicals are delicate and you must be aware of what you have available. Never do a cleansing without verifying the data provided by your own self. Energy balances are also essential in order to check the data provided, use tables, charts and formulas if necessary. If you seem lost, consult your provider and books, if you calculated everything and don't have the same results of your provider, ask for a balance and procedures.

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